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Relation in between Social Media and Well-Being of Elementary Education Teachers

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Keywords : *Social Media Addiction (SMA), Social Networking Site (SNS), Well-being and Elementary Education Teachers etc.*

Abstract

In recent scenario, as Social Media Addiction (SMA) is recognized as major cause of declined psychological, social and physical well-being of our society including teaching professionals. Different Social Networking Sites (SNS) usage has become increasingly pervasive among professional and teachers in the last decade; it was not known if these platforms are positively or negatively related to teacher's mental health and well-being. This study made its effort to analyze significance of uses hours and social media addiction status on well-being of Elementary education teachers. There are approximately 10731 Elementary education teachers working in government elementary school in Prayagraj District in state of Uttar Pradesh .Simple random sampling technique was used to select 256 Elementary education teachers for the study. Social Media Addiction Checklist (SMAC) and Well Being Index (WBI) test scale were used for the study. To find out the objectives particular t-test and ANOVA was applied. Result revealed that in uses hours no significance in well-being. Low level social media addiction status Elementary education teacher have high level of well-being.

Introduction

In modern world social media usage has become increasingly pervasive among professional and teachers in the last decade; it was not known if these platforms are positively or negatively related to teacher's perception of their mental well-being. Thus social media has been taken as great concern in psychological and social researches. During the last 5 years, the number of teenagers using social media has increased dramatically (O' Keffe & Pearson, 2011). Well-being, quality of life, happiness,

life satisfaction and active and positive life style all are issues related to human being that require wider association and greater understanding.

As every human go through their life span and face changes. Ones feel happy and satisfy may another feels isolated, lonely and negatively charged. All have decisions to make and their lives may have to adapt to both their environment and situation for their quality of life and well-being. Chouhan and Sharma, V. (2014) suggest well-being includes the relationship of the mind, sprit and body also explores the psychological dimensions. Thus wellbeing is a positive concept emphasizing particular social and personal resources as well as physical capabilities. Present model, notion of well-being refers to health, vitality, creativity, fulfilment and resilience. It refers to thriving and flourishing that involves mind, body, society and surroundings normally. Well-being refers as harmonious interaction of cognitive and affective process rather than subjugating to them. Well-being in term of Indian nomenclature, it refers to harmony of Indriyas, Chitta and Atma. The Indian approach to well-being refers to Maitri, Karuna, Mudita and Upeksha meaning as Relatedness, Compassion, Pleasant disposition and Avoidance of conflict. In other words, well-being refers to uniting self with self by denying the ego.

Social media are web based communication gadget that allows individuals to interact with each other by both sharing and caring information. Michael Dewing (2010) suggest kinds of internet service commonly associated with social include- Blog, Social bookmarking sites, Status update services, Social Networking Sites (SNS) and Media sharing sites. There are two terms 'Social Media' and 'Social Networking sites'. Media refers to the information we are actually sharing, whether it is a link to an article, a video, an animated GIF, a PDF document, a simple status update or anything else. While networking, adversely, has to do with whom our audience is and the relationships we have with them.

Addiction is a complex situation that leads to negative effects. In other forms of addictions like drugs, gambling, video gaming, overeating etc., people feel bound to particular activities such that they become harmful habits, which can obstruct in their lives of individual who use social media sites excessively (American Psychological Association). Now a days it has been observed that Elementary education teachers were widely using social media compare to before pandemic. Without any proper training, guidelines and monitoring the negative impact explores on students as well as teacher's well-being. Presently using of social media to Elementary education teachers is compulsory and it becomes part of service. This study explores well-being of Elementary Education Teachers to the social media addiction. Government elementary school teacher, who are using smartphone for curricular and co curricular purpose were the respondent. In Prayagraj District there are total 10731 government Elementary Education Teachers working in various rural and urban blocks. Since a large number of populations as govt. Elementary education teachers compare to other academic areas, therefore this

study is greater scope in future in understanding use of social media and their effect on well-being of teachers.

In context of aforesaid the present study will intend to explore the social media addiction and its affect on well-being among Elementary Education Teachers, therefore objective stated as- *To assess the level of well-being among Elementary education teachers in relation with social media.* There are two hypotheses formulated as following-

Ho1 There will be no significant difference in level of well-being of Elementary education teachers in their social media addiction.

Ho2 There will be no significant difference in level of well-being of purpose of using social media.

Reviews

There are various reviews which are directly or indirectly related to considered variables of the present study. The study done by Subhashini and Raju (2021) and quoted that there is a significant association between time spent on social media and the number of social networking apps. Deepa and Priya (2020) concluded that majority of the respondents using number of social networking sites and they are spending time more than four hours in a day for using social networking sites found relationship between feeling anxious and serious active on social networking sites than in real life. Mathewson (2019) reported that there was a weak positive correlation in between the relationship of social media usage and depression and anxiety among undergraduate students. Chouhan and Joshi (2018) in their study found that youth are using more social media as compared to teenagers and they have a low level of well-being. Muflih & Amestiasih (2018) reported insignificant relationship between social media addiction with anxiety and social health disaster risk variables in adolescents. O'Reilly, Dogra e t. al. (2018) quoted that targeting and utilizing social media for promoting mental wellbeing among adolescents and educating youth to manage the possible deleterious effects. Sharma and Sharma (2018) studied on internet addiction and found that significantly negatively correlated to psychological well-being and sub-dimensions of psychological well-being. Masthi and Pruthvi (2017) have also found that Psychological (anger, isolated and frustration) and behavioural (sleep disturbance and abandon personal hygiene) adversity was observed in 67.42% and 51.01% of public and private school pupils respectively. Hawi & Samaha (2016) found and quoted that social media in terms of addictive behaviours adversely related to self-esteem, and the latter had a definitive and conclusive concordance with life satisfaction. Puri and Solanki (2016) studied and explored psychological well-being is slightly negatively correlated with social networking while others are slightly positively correlated with social networking. Mishra, Dangi and Patel (2015) studied and quoted that networking sites and the psychological well-being while positive relationship existed between online perceived social support and psychological well-being. Bolton et al. (2013) have also found in their study that social media use might also have a positive effect on young people's psychological and emotional

well-being and help them to strengthen and nurture supportive relationships with family and friends. Devine & Lloyd (2012) quoted that the use of social networking sites has been reported as leading to lower psychological well-being for girls.

The review of related literature states that many studies conducted on social media and internet addiction. Researchers' explored the relationship of social media addiction and well-being, academic performance, self-esteem, personal relationship, political involvement, mental health etc. Not a single study has been found on this topic where well-being of Elementary education teachers. In India, very few studies had been conducted in the context of well-being in relation to social media. This gap has been highly motivated to conduct a research investigation to know how social media addiction affects well-being of Elementary education teachers.

Methodology

Elementary education teachers who are working in government elementary school of Prayagraj Districts of Uttar Pradesh were the population of the study. Simple random sampling techniques were used in which self-motivated Elementary education teacher responded through online questionnaire. Total 256 (N=256) sample Elementary education teacher were responded stipulated time in which 149 male teachers and 107 female teachers of different subjects. Uses duration (Less/More than 2 hours), Purpose of using social media (Academic/Personal) were the independent and well-being be the dependent variables. The Social Media Addiction Checklist (SMAC) developed by Chouhan & Joshi (2016) and Well-Being Index developed by Chouhan & Sharma (2016) were adopted for assessing social media addiction and well-being respectively. SMAC consists of 40 statements responding in the form of Yes/No and provided 1 and 0 marks respectively. The WBI scale consists of 50 statements and scoring procedure based on 5 point Likert scale. The analysis of collected data comprised of mean by t-test for purpose (Academic and Personal) and social media addiction status (Addict and Non-Addict) on measure of well-being. Obtained results are described under descriptive and inferential analysis by employing SPSS (Version 16) and are discussed under speculated objective and hypothesis in the light of existing literature as following-

Ho1 There will be no significant difference in level of well-being of Elementary education teachers in their social media addiction.

Table-1
Compare Addiction

	Addiction	N	Mean	S.D	SEM	t
Well-being	Social media addicted	65	205.40	18.906	2.345	3.186
	Social media non-addicted	191	213.33	16.769	1.213	

Table-1 shows that the analysis for social media addiction status on considered measure of well-being which is endorsed as significant ($t = 3.186$) because of 't' value is more than table value. More precisely social media addict group of Elementary education teachers were found poorer in their level of well-being ($M = 205.40$) as compared to social media non-addict group of teachers ($M = 213.33$). On the basis of obtained result concluded that over dependency on social media adversely affect well-being of Elementary education teachers. Thus hypothesis Ho1, there will be no significant difference in level of well-being of Elementary education teachers in their social media addiction is rejected.

The result indicated that the social media addicted Elementary education teachers have less mean for level of well-being also Puri and Solanki (2016) pointed that psychological well-being are slightly negatively correlated with social media addiction. Thus the results of the present study support the above review.

Ho2 There will be no significant difference in level of well-being of purpose of using social media.

Table-2
Compare Purpose

	Purpose	N	Mean	S.D	SEM	T
Well-being	Academic	166	213.71	16.860	1.309	2.049
	Personal	27	206.52	17.270	3.324	

Table-2 presents analysis for purpose academic vs. personal on considered measure of well-being which is endorsed as significant ($t = 2.049$) because of ‘t’ value is more than table value. More precisely using personal purpose social media of Elementary education teachers are found poorer in their level of well-being ($M = 206.52$) as compared to academic purpose ($M = 213.71$). On the basis of obtained result concluded that using social media for personal purpose adversely affect well-being of Elementary education teachers. Thus hypothesis Ho2, there will be no significant difference in level of well-being of purpose of using social media rejected. Approximately 50.78% Elementary Education Teachers consider that SNS is giving a platform where persons share their opinion and feeling while 83.20% consider SNS is the need of our society.

Muppudathi (2016) had studied on the impact of whatsapp messenger use on subjective well-being of college students. The results of the study indicated that most of the students are socially detached and started to be isolated and their personality has been changed from extrovert to introvert even though the app provides a lot of happiness to them. Thus the result of the study support that social media addiction respondents were socially detached and started to be isolated.

Result and Conclusion

Social media is popularized as the most common activity in modern era including student and teachers. Social media addict group of Elementary education teachers are found poorer in their level of well-being ($M = 205.40$) as compared to social media non-addict group of teachers ($M = 213.33$). On the basis of obtained result of the study concluded that over dependency on social media adversely affect well-being of Elementary education teachers. The basis purpose of using social networking sites like- academic, entertainment, personal, social and others where academic ($N = 166$) and personal ($N = 27$) purpose compared and found teacher using social media for basic academic purpose compare to personal have high level of well-being.

Present study was conducted to examine the impact of social media on elementary education teacher's well-being issues. Thus in present time social media usage has become increasingly pervasive among teachers; these platforms are negatively related to teacher's well-being. Study also reported that majority of Elementary education teachers were using social media for academic purpose. The present study also indicate that social media addicted group of Elementary education teachers have low level of well-being. Despite this fact that engaging in different forms of social media is a routine activity and benefited children to old age group by increasing communication, social connection, and even technical competence.

Implication

he relationship between social media usage and well-being is very important in understanding the of the SNS needs of Elementary education teachers. Organising social media campaigns for impact of social media usage on well-being of Elementary education teachers. Presenting information about resources available on school should a teacher be experiencing with social media and well-being. Understanding the social media usage can increase comparison, increasing programming and opportunities that encourage appreciation, gratitude, and self-care can help teacher cultivation.

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